

OHLabCAP_Survey

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Dear Colleague,

Welcome to the OHLabCap survey!

The OHLabCap survey is a benchmarking instrument that will provide a description of the One Health (OH) microbiology system by surveying clinical human diagnostic, food, feed and veterinary OH and related National reference laboratories across all EU/EEA countries. The survey is intended to measure the capacity, capability, interoperability, and adaptability across the OH sector. The survey is focused on six priority bacteria and five priority parasites, respectively below:

1. *Campylobacter* spp.
2. *Listeria*
3. *Salmonella* spp.
4. Shiga toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC)
5. *Shigella* spp.
6. *Yersinia* spp.

1. *Cryptosporidium* spp.
2. *Echinococcus granulosus* (*sensu lato*)
3. *Echinococcus multilocularis*
4. *Toxoplasma gondii*
5. *Trichinella* spp.

We will ensure that everyone benefits from insights into the National networks, infrastructure and communication across the entire OH sector. The results from the survey will be published in an **anonymised** "OHLabCap" technical report, which will be disseminated to all

participating laboratories and available on our website (<https://onehealthejp.eu/jip-oh-harmony-cap/>).

Thank you for your cooperation.

*Nadia Boisen and Flemming Scheutz
OH-Harmony-CAP Coordinators*

Instructions for filling out the survey

Due to the wide scope across questions, OHLabCap survey may require more than one person to fill out the survey. If needed, the survey can, at any point, be saved and shared between colleagues so that the responsible person(s) for each of the priority bacteria and parasites can respond.

1. If you need to share the survey link with your colleagues, follow the steps as described in the invitation email
2. Fill out the survey on the basis of your laboratory
3. Data from research projects should not be included. Only include routine and/or surveillance work
4. There are 56 questions and the survey takes approximately 30-40 minutes to fill out

Role of your laboratory

Here, we would like some general information.

- * 1. At what level does your laboratory operate: National, regional or local?

(If needed, check more than one box)

- National
- Regional
- Local
- other

1a. Other:

100 character(s) maximum

- * 2. What source material does your laboratory test?

(If needed, check more than one box)

- Animals

- Humans
- Food / feed
- Environment

* 3. Does your laboratory perform diagnostics, surveillance or both?

(If both, please check both boxes)

- Diagnostics
- Surveillance

* 4. Does your laboratory detect and/or type bacteria, parasites, or both?

(If both, please check both boxes)

- Bacteria
- Parasites

Provision and regulation of microbiology services

Here, the main purpose is to get an idea of your capability and how your laboratory is regulated, organised and funded.

* 5. Are your clinical (human) microbiology laboratory tests funded/reimbursed in total, or in part, either by a national insurance scheme or by a governmental budget?

(If needed, please check more than one box)

- External customers
- For hospital inpatient testing
- For inpatient and outpatient testing
- No tests are reimbursed
- Not relevant

* 5. Are your animal microbiology laboratory tests funded/reimbursed in total, or in part, either by a national insurance scheme or by a governmental budget?

(If needed, please check more than one box)

- Tests are not reimbursed
- Tests are fully reimbursed
- Tests are partly reimbursed
- For commercial activities
- Not relevant

* 5. Are your microbiology laboratory tests funded/reimbursed in total, or in part, either by a national insurance scheme or by a governmental budget?

(If needed, please check more than one box)

- Tests are not reimbursed
- Tests are fully reimbursed
- Tests are partly reimbursed
- For commercial and other (external or funded) activities

Not relevant

* 6. Has the COVID-19 pandemic resulted in a reorganisation and/or transfer of personnel in 2020?

Yes

No

* 7. In what year was the last department reorganisation implemented (*e.g.* 2002)?

(‘Reorganisation’ constitutes a structural and financial change due to strategic priorities)

4 character(s) maximum

* 8. Over the last 10 years, how many times has your department been reorganised?

(Numbers only. ‘Reorganisation’ constitutes a structural and financial change due to strategic priorities)

3 character(s) maximum

* 9. How many academics, supervisors, and technicians are working in your laboratory (staff and temporary staff)?

(Total, numbers only)

10 character(s) maximum

* 10. What is the human population in your laboratory uptake area?

(Numbers only)

50 character(s) maximum

11. How many samples of the **combined** six priority bacteria (*Campylobacter* spp., *Listeria*, *Salmonella* spp., Shiga toxin producing *E. coli*, *Shigella* spp., *Yersinia* spp.) did your laboratory analyse in 2019 and 2020?

(Please include all processed samples, both negative and positive results as one total. Note: positive results include both indirect (*i. e.* antibody) and direct (*i. e.* microscopy, PCR) methods.)

	2019	2020
* Total number of processed samples		

11. How many samples of the **combined** five priority parasites (*Cryptosporidium* spp., *Echinococcus granulosus* (*sensu lato*), *Echinococcus multilocularis*, *Toxoplasma gondii*, *Trichinella* spp.) did your laboratory analyse in 2019 and 2020?

(Please include all processed samples, both negative and positive results as one total. Note: positive results include both indirect (i. e. antibody) and direct (i. e. microscopy, PCR) methods.)

	2019	2020
* Total number of processed samples		

* 12. Is your laboratory accredited according to either ISO 17025, ISO 15189, or equivalent national standards?

(If needed, check more than one box)

- ISO 15189
- ISO 17025
- Equivalent national standards
- Not accredited

* 13. For how many of the six priority bacteria does your laboratory have at least one accredited test for?

* 13. For how many of the five priority parasites does your laboratory have at least one accredited test for?

* 14. How many times can your laboratory upscale (number of isolates) if needed, e.g. in an emergency situation, of the combined six priority bacteria?

- x 2
- x 2-5
- > x 5
- Upscaling not possible

* 14. How many times can your laboratory upscale (number of specimens) if needed, e.g. in an emergency situation, of the combined five priority parasites?

- x 2
- x 2-5
- > x 5
- Upscaling not possible

15. If needed, what is your maximum capacity for typing of the six priority bacteria per week?

	Maximum number of isolates that can be typed per week
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	
* <i>Listeria</i>	
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	

15. If needed, what is your maximum capacity for testing of the five priority parasites per week?

	Maximum number of specimens that can be typed (includes detection/typing) per week
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	

* 16. Does your laboratory have a contingency plan in case of too many samples received?

- Yes
- No

* 17. Does your laboratory have a laboratory information management system (LIMS) available?

- Yes
- No
- Other equivalent to LIMS

17a. Other equivalent:

50 character(s) maximum

* 18. Does your laboratory store sample data?

- Yes
- No

* 18a. How does your laboratory store your sample data?

- Paper
- Digital

* 19. Is your laboratory authorised and/or registered from any health, food, feed or veterinary authority (or professional organisations)?

- Yes
- No
- NA

* 19a. Is this according to legal and/or regulatory requirements?

- Yes
- No

Diagnostic guidelines

20. Does your laboratory perform primary detection from samples (*i.e.* faeces, blood, tissue, food, water) on the six priority bacteria?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

20. Does your laboratory perform primary detection from samples (i.e. faeces, blood, tissue, food, water) on the five priority parasites?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

21. Does your laboratory have national guidelines available for the selection of samples for the detection of the six priority bacteria?

(Note: This could be any kind of guideline for the specific organism or clinical guidelines including priorities of examination of patients with diarrhoea i.e. bloody diarrhoea, certain age groups etc. It could also be the number of recommended tests, herds or animals. The survey just wants to register if guidelines are in place or not.)

	Guidelines are not available at the national level	Guidelines are available without compliance monitoring	Guidelines are implemented with compliance monitoring	Other	Not relevant
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 21a (bacteria). In what year were your current laboratory guidelines published?

21. Does your laboratory have national guidelines available for the five priority parasites?

(Note: This could be any kind of guideline for the specific organism or clinical guidelines including priorities of examination of patients with diarrhoea i.e. bloody diarrhoea, certain age groups etc. It could also be the number of recommended tests, herds or animals. The survey just wants to register if guidelines are in place or not.)

	Guidelines are not available at the national level	Guidelines are available without compliance monitoring	Guidelines are implemented with compliance monitoring	Other	Not relevant
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 21a (parasites). In what year were your current laboratory guidelines published?

4 character(s) maximum

22. Does your laboratory have a national standard protocol for the detection of the six priority bacteria?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

22. Does your laboratory have a national standard protocol for the detection of the five priority parasites?

(*Method as described in Annex I of the REG (EU) 2015/1375 or equivalent. #https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2015/1375/annex_1)

	Yes	No	ISO 18743	EU Reg. 2015/1375*	EURL method as described by ISS#	NA
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
*						

<i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>					
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>					
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>					
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>					

23. Does your laboratory have a method different from the national standard protocol for the detection of the six priority bacteria?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 23a (bacteria). What other method for detection is utilized?

(If needed, please check more than one box)

- Commercial kits
- In-house method
- Method according to published literature

23. Does your laboratory have a method different from the national standard protocol for the detection of the five priority parasites?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 23a (parasites). What other method for detection is utilized?

(If needed, please check more than one box)

- Commercial kits
- In-house method
- Method according to published literature

24. How many of the six priority bacteria did your laboratory type (both culture and molecular) in 2019 and 2020?

	Number of isolates typed in 2019	Number of isolates typed in 2020
C <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.		
L <i>Listeria</i>		
S <i>Salmonella</i> spp.		
S higa toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>		
S <i>higella</i> spp.		
Y <i>ersinia</i> spp.		

24. How many of the five priority parasites did your laboratory type in 2019 and 2020?

	Number of samples typed in 2019	Number of samples typed in 2020
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.		
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>		
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>		
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>		
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.		

25. How many bacterial isolates did your laboratory type (both culture and molecular) in 2019 and 2020?

(Please include all bacterial isolates both the six priority bacteria and other bacteria)

	2019	2020
* Total number of isolates		

25. How many parasites did your laboratory type in 2019 and 2020?

(Please include all parasite isolates both the five priority parasites and other parasites)

	2019	2020
* Total number of samples		

26. What level of typing does your laboratory perform on the six priority bacteria?

	Phenotypical (including biochemical reactions and microscopy)	Molecular	Both phenotypical and molecular	Not relevant
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

26. What level of typing does your laboratory perform on the five priority parasites?

	Phenotypical (including biochemical reactions and microscopy)	Molecular	Both phenotypical and molecular	Not relevant
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

27. How does your laboratory type the six priority bacteria?

(If needed, please check more than one box)

	Serotyping	Virulence genes by PCR or RT-PCR	Multi Locus Variable number of tandem repeats analysis (MLVA)	Restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) PCR	Other	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>					
<i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

* 27a (bacteria). In what year was the current PCR/RT-PCR method implemented?

* 27b (bacteria). Other typing methods

500 character(s) maximum

27. How does your laboratory type the five priority parasites?

(If needed, please check more than one box)

	PCR and/or RT-PCR	Single locus	Multi locus	MLST	WGS	Other	NA
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> (<i>sensu lato</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>						

* 27a (parasites). In what year was the current PCR/RT-PCR method implemented?

* 27b (parasites). Other typing methods

500 character(s) maximum

Antimicrobial drug susceptibility testing

* 28. Does your laboratory perform AMR testing on *Salmonella* spp. and zoonotic thermophilic *Campylobacter* (*C.*

jejuni, *C. coli* and *C. lari*)?

(If needed, please check more than one box)

- Yes, *Campylobacter* spp.
- Yes, *Salmonella* spp.
- No, *Campylobacter* spp.
- No, *Salmonella* spp.

* 28a. Which clinical breakpoints does your laboratory use for interpretive reporting of antibacterial drug susceptibility?

- CLSI clinical breakpoints
- EUCAST clinical breakpoints
- NA

* 29. How does your laboratory perform AMR testing?

(If needed, check more than one box)

- Diffusion based methods
- Minimal Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

* 29a. Which MIC determination method does your laboratory use?

- Microdilution
- Gradient strip
- Both microdilution and gradient strip

Provision and regulation of national reference microbiology services

* 30. Is your laboratory allowed to share source identifiable data (i. e. person, herd, company food source) with other authorities in case of an outbreak?

- Yes
- No

31. Does your laboratory have the capacity to store the six priority bacteria (e.g. isolates, DNA, stool, tissue) for more than two weeks?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

31a (bacteria). If yes, how long does your laboratory have the capacity to store the six priority bacteria?

	Two weeks	12 months	> 1 year	NA

* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<i>Listeria</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

31. Does your laboratory have the capacity to store the five priority parasites (e.g. specimens, DNA, stool, tissue)?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

31a (parasites). If yes, how long does your laboratory have the capacity to store the five priority parasites?

	Two weeks	12 months	> 1 year	NA
<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

32. Does your laboratory have the capacity to store sequence data from the six priority bacteria?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

32. Does your laboratory have the capacity to store sequence data from the five priority parasites?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

33. Does your laboratory utilise subcontractors, partnerships, or equivalent for the characterisation and/or analysis of the six priority bacteria?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

33. Does your laboratory utilise subcontractors, partnerships, or equivalent for the characterisation and/or analysis of the five priority parasites?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) for diagnostics and/or surveillance

34. Does your laboratory use WGS-based typing of the six priority bacteria?

	No WGS performed but a WGS plan is in progress	WGS is used occasionally	WGS is used routinely	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

34a (bacteria). What kind of typing information does your laboratory extract from the WGS of the six priority bacteria?

(If needed, please check more than one box)

	Serotyping	Virulence genes	Multiple locus variable number of Sequence type (ST)	Core genome multilocus sequence typing (cgMLST)	Whole genome multilocus sequence typing (wgMLST)	Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNP) analysis	Speciation	Other	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

34. Does your laboratory use WGS-based typing of the five priority parasites?

	No WGS performed but a WGS plan is in progress	WGS is used occasionally	WGS is used routinely	NA
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

34a (parasites). Does your laboratory use WGS for characterization and speciation of the five priority parasites?

	Yes	No	Occasionally
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

National surveillance networks

* 35. Do you know your in-country One Health counterparts?

(Note: For example, if a human clinical laboratory, do you know your food/feed and/or animal counterpart(s) or vice-versa)

- Yes, local
- Yes, national
- Both local and national
- No

* 36. Do you communicate or have meetings with your counterparts?

- Yes
- No

* 36a. How often do you communicate or have meetings with your counterparts?

- Weekly
- Monthly
- Quarterly
- Biannually

- Annually
- When needed
- NA

* 37. Does your laboratory support the coordination of reporting across One Health sectors *i.e.* National zoonoses report?

- Yes
- No
- NA

38. Which of the six priority bacteria are **laboratory-notifiable** in your country. Please answer based on laboratory findings not on clinical diagnosis or suspicion.

(Note: Answering "detection without isolation" means, for example, use of a commercial kit or extraction of DNA from specimen (faeces, blood, tissue etc.))

	Yes, only isolates	Yes, only detection without isolation	Yes, both isolates and detection without isolates	No	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

38. Which of the five priority parasites are **laboratory-notifiable** in your country. Please, answer based on laboratory findings not on clinical diagnosis or suspicion.

(Note: Answering "detection without isolation" means, for example, use of commercial kit or extraction of DNA from specimen (faeces, blood, tissue etc.))

	Yes, only isolates	Yes, only detection without isolation	Yes, both isolates and detection without isolation	No	NA
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

39. Does your laboratory report data on the six priority bacteria into a **national** surveillance database?

	Yes	Yes, data from the whole country	No, only partial, local /regional	None	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 39a (bacteria). How are the results reported?

(If needed, please check more than one box)

- Digital
- Paper
- Phone

* 39b (bacteria). How often are the national surveillance results reported?

- Weekly report
- Monthly report
- Quarterly report
- Biannual or annual report
- Webpage (continuously)
- Not nationally

39. Does your laboratory report data on the five priority parasites into a **national** surveillance database?

	Yes	Yes, data from the whole country	No, only partial, local /regional	None	NA
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> (<i>sensu lato</i>)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 39a (parasites). How are the results reported?

(If needed, please check more than one box)

- Digital
- Paper
-

Phone

* 39b (parasites). How often are the national surveillance results reported?

- Weekly report
- Monthly report
- Quarterly report
- Biannual or annual report
- Webpage (continuously)
- Not nationally

* 40. Does your laboratory have confidentiality agreements across the One Health sector on the six priority bacteria?

- Yes
- No
- NA

* 40. Does your laboratory have confidentiality agreements across the One Health sector on the five priority parasites?

- Yes
- No
- NA

Active participation in EU disease networks

41. Did your laboratory actively participate in an EU disease network organized by ECDC, EFSA, or the EU Commission in 2019 and/or 2020?

(If needed, please check more than one box)

	The EU Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF)	Food- and waterborne (FWD) ECDC disease network	External quality assessments (EQA)	Annual meeting	European Reference Laboratories (EURL) Foodborne Bacteria	Other	No participation	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

41a (bacteria). Other networks

200 character(s) maximum

41. Did your laboratory actively participate in an EU disease network organized by ECDC, EFSA, or the EU Commission in 2019 and/or 2020?

(If needed, please check more than one box)

	The EU Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF)	Food- and waterborne (FWD) ECDC Disease Network	External Quality Assessments (EQA)	Annual meeting	European Union Reference Laboratories (EURL) Foodborne Parasites	Other	No participation	NA
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> (<i>sensu lato</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

41a (parasites). Other networks

200 character(s) maximum

42. What is the criteria for reporting the six priority bacteria to the EU networks?

	Routine	Suspicion of an outbreak	No reporting	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

42. What is the criteria for reporting the five priority parasites to the EU networks?

	Routine	Suspicion of an outbreak	No reporting	NA
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

43. Which authority do you report the surveillance results to?

(If needed, please check more than one box)

	European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC)	National Surveillance authorities (epidemiologists etc.)	National Reference Laboratory (NRL)	No reporting
* <i>Campylobacter spp.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Salmonella spp.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

43. Which authority do you report the surveillance results to?

(If needed, please check more than one box)

	European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC)	National Surveillance authorities (epidemiologists etc.)	National Reference Laboratory (NRL)	No reporting
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

National outbreak response support

* 44. Does personnel from your laboratory participate as a member in a foodborne outbreak investigation team?

- Yes
- No
- NA
- On request

* 45. Does your laboratory have trained personnel available for assistance during an outbreak with national level teams?

- No personnel available
- Personnel available during working hours
- Personnel available in 24/7 duty roster
- NA

46. Does your laboratory share data across One Health sectors (e.g. diagnostic, typing, and characterisation) from the six priority bacteria with other authorities?

	Yes	Yes, but only during outbreaks	No	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

46. Does your laboratory share data across One Health sectors (e.g. diagnostic, typing, and characterisation) from the five priority parasites with other authorities?

	Yes	Yes, but only during outbreaks	No	NA
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

47. Do you have a contingency plan for the six priority bacteria during an outbreak?

--	--	--

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin producing <i>E. coli</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

47. Do you have a contingency plan for the five priority parasites during an outbreak?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 48. Do you receive information from any authority in the event of an outbreak?

(i.e. this will include alerts and ongoing information about current outbreaks)

- Yes
- No
- NA

Communications

* 49. Does your Institute have a website or newsletter?

- Yes
- No
- NA

* 50. How does your laboratory disseminate your diagnostic and typing results?

- International
- National
- No dissemination

* 51. Does your laboratory communicate with the public?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

* 52. Does your institute have a press/media communication team?

- Yes
- No
- NA

Contact information

Note: Results from this survey will be anonymised and participants will be given a random number. This number may be shared with the participant on request.

* 53. Name of institution

100 character(s) maximum

* 54. Country

50 character(s) maximum

* 55. Contact person

50 character(s) maximum

* 56. Contact person email address

50 character(s) maximum

Final comments

Is there anything else you wish to add to the information you have provided?

1000 character(s) maximum

Acknowledgement

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